

A Study on Financial Performance of Futuristic Trends of Urban Cooperative Banks in India

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Sathish, G. "A Study on Financial Performance of Futuristic Trends of Urban Cooperative Banks in India." *Shanlax International Journals of Management*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 1–11.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567671>

Dr. G. Sathish

Assistant Professor, Vijay Institute of Management

Introduction

Tamil Nadu is the pioneering State in introducing the Cooperative Movement for uplifting the poor and downtrodden (*Government of Tamil Nadu: 2013-14 p.24*). The State of Tamil Nadu, which was formally called Madras Province, takes pride initiating the cooperative movement in this country. In Tamil Nadu, UCBs were organized after their enactment of the Cooperative Credit Societies Act 1904. Tamil Nadu can be at its to pride to the fact that the "first urban bank, called "Kancheepuram Urban Cooperative Bank" was established at Kancheepuram. The Cooperative Credit Societies Act of 1912 permitted the registration of federal Institutions and in 1917, there was a special provision made for the admission of cooperative societies as members of the bank. Under 1919 Administrative Reforms Act, cooperatives were made as Provincial subject making each Province responsible for cooperative development. The Madras Cooperative Societies Act of 1932 was the first piece of legislation in the State, later it was amended in the year 1961 and again in 1983 as Tamil Nadu Cooperative Societies Act 1983 which came in to force from 4th April 1988.

In Tami Nadu also, the functions of UCBs were influenced by the recommendations of various Committees and Commissions appointed by RBI, Government of India and State Government. The State Government has also signed the Memorandum of Understanding with the Reserve Bank of India to improve the functioning of UCBs. Accordingly, all the UCBs and their branches have been computerized. Core Banking Solution for all the UCBs and their branches is under implementation in order to improve their operational efficiency and to provide better services to the customers (*Government of Tamil Nadu: 2016-17, p.34*).

Grade-wise Distribution of UCBs in India

UCBs are graded into four categories on the basis of their financial performance. The financial performance is determined by various parameters including capital adequacy, the level of NPAs and history

International Conference on “Contemporary Issues and Futuristic Trends in Management” (CIFTM’19)
of profit/loss. While UCBs from Grade I and II can be considered as relatively stronger banks, the banks belonging to Grades III and IV can be classified as sick or weak banks (*RBI:2008-09, p.159*).

Table 2.1 Grade wise Classification of the UCBs in India

(Figures in numbers)

Year	No of banks in Grade				No of UCBs
	Grade-I	Grade-II	Grade-III	Grade-IV	
2006-07	652 (35.96)	598 (32.98)	295 (16.27)	268 (14.78)	1813 (100)
2007-08	748 (42.26)	526 (29.71)	258 (14.58)	238 (13.45)	1770 (100)
2008-09	845 (49.10)	484 (28.12)	219 (12.73)	173 (10.05)	1721 (100)
2009-10	879 (52.51)	465 (27.78)	179 (10.69)	151 (9.02)	1674 (100)
2010-11	845 (51.37)	497 (30.21)	172 (10.46)	131 (7.96)	1645 (100)
2011-12	585 (36.16)	694 (42.89)	227 (14.03)	112 (6.92)	1618 (100)
2012-13	314 (19.55)	861 (53.61)	232 (14.45)	99 (6.16)	1606 (100)
2013-14	392 (24.67)	805 (50.66)	251 (15.80)	81 (5.10)	1589 (100)
2014-15	449 (28.44)	791 (50.10)	263 (16.66)	76 (4.81)	1579 (100)
2015-16	406 (25.79)	824 (52.35)	274 (17.41)	70 (4.45)	1574 (100)

Source: Report on the Trend and Progress of Banking in India for various years.

Note: Figures in parenthesis are percentage to total UCBs.

It was found that as an outcome of the consolidation process of the UCBs in the form of merger/acquisition among financially viable banks and exit of the non-viable ones, there was a concentration of a number of UCBs in grade I and II categories in recent years. The percentage of banks in grade I and II together constituted 78 per cent of total UCBs as at the end of March 2015-16 compared to 68.95 per cent at the end of March 31, 2006-07. However, there was marginal decline in the percentage of UCBs of Grade-I category in 2015-16 as compared to the last ten years. Graph 2.1 shows the position of Financially Viable and Weaker UCBs based on their financial performance.

Funds Mobilized by UCBs in India

The working funds play a vital role to keep the banks in their going condition. The different sources of working funds mobilized by UCBs of India consisted of share capital, reserve fund, deposit and borrowings. The optimum size of the working funds and the banks efficiency in strategically applying the funds would have long term effect on the volume of business. Inefficient management of working funds would negatively affect the banking transactions, profitability and the viability of the bank. The trend in funds position of UCBs in India is given in *table 2.2*:

Table 2.2 Funds mobilized by UCBs in India (As on 31st March)
(Rs. in Crore)

Year	Share capital	Reserve Fund	Deposit	Borrowings	Working capital
2006-07	3884.67 (2.67)	10867.21 (7.48)	120983.62 (83.24)	2602.75 (1.79)	145336.33
2007-08	4658.23 (2.81)	14841.19 (8.97)	138496.19 (83.79)	2292.43 (1.39)	165287.19
2008-09	5261.51 (2.78)	15591.26 (8.24)	158733.41 (83.92)	2554.89 (1.35)	189139.31
2009-10	5567.71 (2.47)	24531.92 (10.87)	183150.28 (81.19)	2340.14 (1.04)	225588.94
2010-11	6267.13 (2.45)	26260.25 (10.26)	212031.36 (82.87)	4289.63 (1.67)	255847.80
2011-12	7300.04 (2.57)	27000.16 (9.49)	238500.61 (83.86)	3600.24 (1.27)	284400.21
2012-13	8047.45 (2.49)	25690.22 (7.94)	276830.29 (85.64)	2687.10 (0.83)	323254.11
2013-14	8972.28 (2.50)	24353.61 (6.79)	317769.22 (88.60)	2552.18 (0.71)	358646.83
2014-15	9954.47 (2.49)	27375.62 (6.84)	355134.18 (88.84)	2246.81 (0.56)	399709.62
2015-16	11007.31 (2.51)	29595.15 (6.74)	392179.01 (89.25)	2615.21 (0.60)	439396.03
CGR	11.9	9.9	14.3	0	13.8
2020	14473.21	40128.23	530707.23	2785.22	588096.21
2025	18358.05	49348.36	684037.94	2888.05	754536.03

Source: Report on the Trend and Progress of Banking in India for various years.

Note: Figures in parenthesis are percentage to Working Capital

Share Capital

Share capital is one of the primary sources of internal capital of UCBs. The paid-up share capital of a bank was an important factor which determines its maximum borrowing power for raising resources for its operations (*NABARD: 2003, p.87*). RBI guidelines stipulated that a minimum of 2.5 percent of the loan amount as the share capital contribution in case of a secured advance and 5 percent of the loan amount in case of an unsecured advance (*RBI: 2008, p.29*) to be mobilized from borrowers.

As depicted in Table 2.2, it was found that the position of share capital of UCBs in India shows an increasing trend registering a compound growth rate of 11.9 per cent. The reason for the increasing trend was due to the linkage between loan disbursement and share capital contribution. Further, based on the current trend in share capital, projected share capital was estimated to be Rs.14473.21 crore in 2020 and Rs. 18358.05 crore in 2025.

Reserve Fund

Reserve Fund formed has been second important source of the working capital for UCBs (*Nakkiran, S. & John Winfred, A: 1988, p.173*) which was set aside from the earnings of the banks to meet the future contingencies. The reserve fund maintained by UCBs included Statutory Reserve Fund, Building Fund, Dividend Equalization Fund, Special Bad Debts reserves, Bad and Doubtful Debts, NPA provisions, Common Good Fund, Employees Relief Fund, etc.

The position of reserve fund of the UCBs in India showed two fold increases during the period under study. In the year 2006-07 the position of reserve fund was Rs. 10867.21 crore which increased to Rs 29595.15 crore in 2015-16 registered a compound growth rate of 9.9 per cent (*Table 2.2*).

Deposit

The central pillar of all banking institutions especially the UCBs is Deposit of various types and this is element constituted more than 90 per cent of the working capital of the UCBs. In fact, ‘Deposit’ is the key element of banking business and this core capital element and served as the backbone of economic development of the country (*RBI: 2008, p. 116*). Deposit is an important indicator of the success and efficiency of the credit agency (*Nakkiran, S. & John Winfred, A: 1988. P. 293*). The improvement in public confidence in banking sector is reflected on the rise in deposit base of the UCBs.

At all India level, the position of deposits had been increased from Rs. 120983.62 crore in 2006-07 to Rs. 392179.01 crore during the year 2015-16 and the annual growth value is 14.3 per cent. In future, the deposit would increase Rs 530707.23 crore in the year 2020 and Rs 684037.94 crore in the year 2025 (*Table 2.2*).

Borrowings

UCBs can borrow funds from DCCBs. If they are not able to meet their demands out of their own resources, their borrowings from DCCBs became inevitable. The working Group on Industrial credit through Cooperative Banks appointed by the RBI had recommended that RBI should provide refinance facilities under section 17(2) (bb) of its Act (now section 21 (1) (V) / 3 (a) (VI) of NABARD Act of 1981) to UCBs in respect of their working capital advances and Small Scale and Cottage Industries. The apex banks can directly allot funds to the UCBs or funds from the apex banks may be routed through the DCCBs depending on the arrangements preferred by the UCBs (*Nakkiran & John Winfred: 1988.p.169*).

The position of borrowings of UCBs in India showed a fluctuating trend during the study period. Borrowings constituted a relatively meager source of funds for both scheduled and non-scheduled UCBs. However, the projections in the borrowings may increase Rs 2785.22 crore in 2020 and Rs. 2888.05 crore in 2025 (Table 2.2), if the current trend continues in the future also.

Working Capital

The Working Capital is the key fund around which the whole banking business is operated (RBI: 2008, p.36). The sources of working capital of UCBs consisted of share capital, entrance fees, reserves and other funds, deposits from members and non-members of cooperatives and borrowings from DCCBs, NABARD and Government.

Working Capital position of UCBs in India showed an increasing trend during the study period which was increased from Rs. 145336.33 crore to Rs 439396.03 crore 2015-16. Deposits constituted more than 90 percent of the total working capital in all the years of the study period. In future, the position of working capital may increase to Rs 588096.21 crore in 2020 and Rs 754536.03 crore in 2025 (Table -2.2).

Graph 2.1

Deployment of Resources by UCBs in India

Deployment of resources by UCBs in India consisted of investments and loans and advances. These resources play an important role in the gross earnings of urban banks, and promote the economic development of the country. The trend of deployment of resources by UCBs in India represents the *table 2.3*.

**Table 2.3 Deployment of Resources by UCBs in India
(Rs.in crore)**

Year	Loans and Advances	Investment
2006-07	78660.34	47316.41
2007-08	88981.13	60123.12
2008-09	97918.81	64171.73
2009-10	112436.16	79170.96
2010-11	136341.74	87075.41
2011-12	158000.86	88000.74
2012-13	181031.91	108518.08
2013-14	200352.05	115310.14

2014-15	224329.23	123071.08
2015-16	245013.53	120911.33
CGR	14.3	11.2
2020	335637.21	172716.54
2025	432127.74	216589.85

Source: Report on the Trend and Progress of Banking in India for various years.

Investment

According to the data source, investments made by UCBs in SLR securities (nearly 90 per cent) showed an increasing trend whereas the investment made in non-SLR securities shows a declining trend during the study period. Investments in Central and State Governments securities constituted almost above 70 per cent of total SLR investments during the study period. Further, investment in terms of deposits with SCBs and DCCBs constituted almost one-fifth of total SLR investment of UCBs.

The position of investment of UCBs showed an increasing trend. In 2006-07 the investment was stood at Rs. 47316.41 crore which increased to Rs. 120911.33 crore at the end of the study period registered a compound growth rate of 11.2 per cent. In future, the projection of investment may increase Rs.172716.54 crore in 2020 and Rs 216589.85 crore in 2025 (Table 2.3).

Loans and Advances

One of the most essential sources of income of the UCB is its loans and advance. It is one of the central functions or services of the Bank towards the economic growth of the country particularly in its area of operation (*RBI: 2008, p.45*).

The position of loans and advances made by UCBs in India had recorded an increasing trend during the study period. There had been an increase from Rs 78660.34 crore in 2006-07 to Rs 245013.53 crore in the year 2015-16. The substantial growth in loans and advances of UCBs confirmed that these banks have been playing a pivotal role in the promotion of urban entrepreneurs. A peculiar feature of the lending trend in UCBs is that more than 50 per cent of the deposits of UCBs are being deployed for loans to the priority sectors and credit to the small borrowers and weaker sections of the society (Table-2.3).

The need for UCBs for providing credit to priority sectors had been examined by the Standing Advisory Committee for UCBs, constituted by Reserve Bank of India in May 1983. The recommendations of the Committee were accepted by Reserve Bank of India. Accordingly the targets for lending to priority sector and weaker sections by the UCBs were stipulated (*RBI: 2007-08, p.126*).

The UCBs are expected to lend not less than 40 percent of their total advances to the priority sector. Besides, it will be ensured that at least 10 percent of the priority sector lending shall be disbursed to the weaker sections of the community. It was found from the table 2.5 the position of priority sector advances made by UCBs have increased from Rs 44058.11 crore in 2006-07 to 124418.55 crore in 2015-16 registering an 11.9 per cent CGR. Also the advances to priority sector by the UCBs constituted more than 50 per cent of their total advances during the study period.

The compositions of credit to sub-targets of priority sector by UCBs suggest that small enterprises and the housing sector occupy the major portion of sub-targets during the study period. Further, they had a share around 70 per cent in the total priority sector credit of UCBs. The share of advances to the agriculture and micro sector remained almost stable. It showed that UCBs in India has been deploying its funds in the form of loans and advances as per the RBI guidelines.

**Table 2.4 Position of Priority Sector and Non-Priority Sector lending by UCBs in India
(Rs. in Crore)**

Year	Sub targets of priority sector					Priority (i)	Non-priority sector (ii)	Total Loan and advances (i+ii)
	Agriculture	Micro and Small enterprise	Housing	Micro Loan	Others			
2006-07	2190.51 (2.80)	6079.39 (7.70)	10247.75 (13.00)	2034.07 (2.6)	23508.03 (29.89)	44058.11 (56.01)	34602.17 (43.99)	78660.23 (100)
2007-08	5363.39 (6.00)	15011.00 (16.90)	11916.12 (13.40)	3012.15 (3.4)	11557.16 (12.99)	46859.05 (52.66)	42122.03 (47.34)	88981.41 (100)
2008-09	4731.12 (4.80)	21283.26 (21.7)	13882.05 (14.20)	3130.70 (3.2)	12222.74 (12.48)	55248.37 (56.42)	42670.65 (43.58)	97918.52 (100)
2009-10	6383.38 (5.80)	29279.11 (26.50)	17923.22 (16.20)	4779.32 (4.3)	13021.04 (11.58)	71385.08 (63.49)	41051.08 (36.51)	112436.47 (100)
2010-11	5078.20 (3.72)	35061.07 (25.71)	17062.31 (12.51)	4090.15 (3.00)	13276.32 (10.74)	74567.27 (54.69)	136341.15 (45.31)	136341.15 (100)
2011-12	5800.51 (3.70)	36600.45 (23.1)	18300.73 (11.60)	1420.22 (9.0)	12100.66 (11.66)	77000.06 (55.06)	81000.38 (44.94)	158000.27 (100)
2012-13	6800.75 (3.80)	42500.09 (23.50)	19500.36 (10.80)	1380.92 (7.6)	12700.62 (10.06)	85300.03 (52.64)	95731.26 (47.36)	181031.84 (100)
2013-14	5791.09 (2.90)	46057.64 (23.07)	20648.07 (10.34)	3212.01 (1.61)	21879.58 (10.92)	97587.27 (51.71)	102765.25 (51.29)	200352.99 (100)
2014-15	5550.17 (2.50)	52307.26 (23.30)	22904.00 (10.20)	4886.64 (2.2)	25174.17 (11.22)	110821.01 (50.40)	113508.21 (50.60)	224329.14 (100)
2015-16	6231.56 (2.54)	58725.63 (23.97)	25715.15 (10.50)	5486.48 (2.24)	28261.43 (11.53)	124418.55 (50.78)	120595.94 (49.22)	245013.15 (100)
CGR	6.9	23.0	9.6	10.7	6.2	11.9	16.1	14.3

Source: Report on the Trend and Progress of Banking in India for various years.

Note: Figures in parenthesis are percentage to total Loans and Advances

Graph 2.2

Non-Performing Assets (NPA) of UCBs in India

As per the prudential norms laid down by RBI “An asset is considered as “Non-Performing” if interest on installments of principal due remains unpaid for more than 180 days. From March 31, 2004, it has been decided to adopt 90 days, overdue norm for identification of NPAs. Banks are required to classify the loans assets into four categories such as

- Standard assets
- Sub-standard assets
- Doubtful assets
- Loss assets

Table 2.5 Non-Performing Assets of UCBs in India

Year	Gross NPA (Rs in Crore)	Gross NPA (%)	Net NPA (Rs. in Crore)	Net NPA (%)	Provisions	Provision cover ratio
2006-07	13363.41	17.0	6044.21	7.70	7319.20	54.77
2007-08	14583.25	16.4	6685.46	9.10	7897.79	54.16
2008-09	13043.93	13.3	5318.95	6.10	7724.98	59.22
2009-10	11399.37	10.1	3821.21	3.90	7578.16	66.48
2010-11	11529.22	8.50	3130.03	2.50	8399.19	72.85
2011-12	11100.64	8.40	2900.54	2.00	8200.10	73.87
2012-13	10900.81	6.00	2530.12	1.40	8370.69	76.79
2013-14	11500.04	5.74	4146.11	2.17	7353.93	63.95
2014-15	13802.72	6.15	6105.23	2.84	7697.49	55.77
2015-16	16056.46	6.55	7141.06	3.05	8915.40	55.52
CGR	0.2	-	-0.9	-	0.9.	-
Future Projections						
2020	15324.24	-	6783.35	-	8540.89	-
2025	16707.71	-	7780.96	-	8926.75	-

Source: Trend and Progress of Banking in India, for Various Years

It was found that (*table 2.5*) the position of both Gross NPA and Net NPA showed a declining trend from 2006-07 to 2012-13. The same trend was observed in the case of provisioning also. The reasons for such a declining trend confirm that the quality of performing assets was quite good. However, there was a gradual increase in Gross NPA and Net NPA from 2013-14 to 2015-16.

Number of UCBs and Membership in Tamil Nadu

UCBs in Tamil Nadu provide banking services and credit facilities to the people living in urban and semi-urban areas. These banks mobilize deposits from the public and extend credit facilities to members such as small traders, artisans and persons belonging to middle-income group for purposes like housing, business and other non-farm sector activities (*Government of Tamil Nadu:2015-16, p.20*). The number of UCBs in Tami Nadu and the membership position is given table 2.6:

**Table 2.6 Position of Membership of UCBs in Tamil Nadu
(Figures in Numbers)**

Year	Number of UCBs	Number of Members
2006-07	128	1624140
2007-08	128	1625008
2008-09	125	1672523
2009-10	125	1751491
2010-11	128	1808467
2011-12	120	1904725
2012-13	120	2145213
2013-14	120	2187241
2014-15	120	2214577
2015-16	120	2315742
CGR	-1.2	4.5
Future Projections		
2020	113	2797619
2025	108	3248083

Source: Compiled from the records of RBI for various years

During the year 2005-06, 128 UCBs existed in Tamil Nadu which decreased to 120 in 2011-12 and remain at same level till today. However, the number of members had been increased from 1624140 in 2006-07 to 2315742 at the end of the study period registering a CGR 4.5 per cent. This showed that the Tamil Nadu UCBs have the strong membership base.

Funds Mobilized by UCBs in Tamil Nadu

Mobilization of funds is an important criterion for UCBs in Tamil Nadu. The funds of UCBs consisted of share capital, reserve fund, deposit, borrowings and working capital. The trend in funds position of UCBs in Tamil Nadu is given in table 2.7:

**Table 2.7 Trend in the Funds Position of UCBs in Tamil Nadu
(Rs in Crores)**

Year	Share capital	Reserve Fund	Deposit	Borrowings	Working Capital
2006-07	142.42 (4.33)	99.81 (3.04)	2892.73 (88.11)	28.29 (0.86)	3283.25
2007-08	146.58 (4.40)	106.71 (3.20)	2910.22 (87.33)	88.82 (2.67)	3332.33
2008-09	148.33 (4.05)	113.74 (3.11)	3203.87 (87.50)	95.46 (2.60)	3661.40
2009-10	151.40 (3.72)	127.03 (3.12)	3569.60 (87.71)	121.59 (2.99)	4069.62

2010-11	154.22 (3.24)	132.86 (2.79)	4373.72 (91.87)	139.74 (2.93)	4760.54
2011-12	173.32 (3.20)	145.27 (2.68)	4841.98 (89.47)	171.52 (3.17)	5412.09
2012-13	182.09 (2.88)	154.67 (2.44)	5919.36 (93.64)	155.05 (2.45)	6321.17
2013-14	202.86 (2.46)	163.28 (1.98)	7646.95 (92.73)	123.59 (1.50)	8246.68
2014-15	224.07 (2.67)	178.21 (2.13)	7929.02 (94.72)	114.10 (1.36)	8371.40
2015-16	247.75 (2.92)	197.91 (2.33)	8244.76 (94.40)	99.94 (1.17)	8497.67
CGR	6.4	7.6	14.3	9.6	13.8
2020	273.86	230.81	10850.60	170.16	11450.05
2025	330.66	283.11	14215.10	203.31	14923.25

Source: Compiled from the record of RBI for various years

Note: Figures in parenthesis are Percentage to Working Capital

The share capital position of UCBs increased from Rs 142.42 crore in 2006-07 to Rs. 247.75 crore in 2015-16 registering a CGR of 6.4 per cent. There was a gradual increase of reserve fund which rose from Rs 99.81 crore in 2006-07 to 197.91 crore in 2015-16 with a CGR of 7.6 per cent. There was a phenomenal increase in the position of deposit throughout the study period i.e., it increased from Rs 2892.73 crore in 2006-07 to Rs 8244.76 crore in 2015-16 with a CGR of 14.3 per cent. Also deposit occupied the major portion of working capital. The position of borrowings ranged between the Rs.28.29 crore in 2006-07 to 99.94 crore. The position of working capital it increased from Rs 3282.25 crore to Rs. 8497.67 crore with a CGR of 13.8 per cent.

In future the position of share capital would increase Rs 273.86 crore in 2020 and Rs 330.66 crore in the year 2025. Simultaneously the Reserve Fund may also increase from Rs 230.81 crore in 2020 and Rs.283.11 crore in 2025 and the position of deposit may be increased to Rs 10850.69 crore in 2020 and Rs 14215.10 crore in 2025.

Lending Operations and NPA of UCBs in Tamil Nadu

The trend of loans and advances of UCBs in Tamil Nadu is given in *table-2.8*:

Table 2.8 Lending operations of UCBs in Tamil Nadu
(Rs in Crore)

Year	Loan issue	Loan outstanding	Gross NPA
2006-07	1377.94	1458.83	115.68
2007-08	1722.31	1815.84	129.53
2008-09	2072.31	2220.09	141.91
2009-10	2307.18	2592.81	163.91

2010-11	2515.25	2725.52	174.72
2011-12	2617.88	3218.67	180.30
2012-13	2921.45	3688.28	197.74
2013-14	3218.21	3968.61	254.01
2014-15	3534.62	4184.34	267.76
2015-16	3968.67	4467.98	286.01
CGR	9.6	13.0	10.7
2020	4965.76	5928.37	373.5
2025	6171.16	7630.94	469.5

Source: RBI

It was found from the table 2.8 that there was a phenomenal growth on the position of loans and advances made by UCBs in Tamil Nadu. The loan issued by UCBs has increased from Rs. 1377.94 in 2006-07 to Rs.3968.87 crore in 2015-16 registering a CGR of 9.6 per cent. The loan outstanding position was increased from Rs 1458.83 crore in 2006-07 to Rs 4467.98 crore in 2015-16 with CGR of 13.0 per cent. At the same time the position of NPA had also increased simultaneously which stood Rs 286.01 crore in the year 2015-16 as against Rs 115.68 crore in the year 2006-07 registering a CGR 10.7 per cent.

In future, the position of issue of loans would increase to Rs 4965.76 crore in 2020 and Rs 6171.16 crore in the year 2025. The loan outstanding position of UCBs in Tamil Nadu may increase to Rs. 5928.37 crore in 2020 and Rs. 7630.94 in the year 2025 at the same time the position of NPA would also increase to Rs.373.50 crore in 2020 and Rs.469.50 crore in the year 2025.

Conclusion

The extension of BR Act to cooperatives was the milestone in the history and growth of UCBs. The growth in deposit and loan outstanding have facilitated for the proper capital formation of these banks. However, the increase in loan outstanding and NPAs of UCBs became the biggest challenge before them. Despite the fact that their growth was heterogeneous and lopsided, they have glittering future even in the competitive market situation prevailing in the banking industry in the current economic environment scenario.

References

1. Government of Madras (1940), *the Report of the Committee on Cooperative*, Madras.
2. Government of Tamil Nadu (2012-13), *Cooperation, Food and Consumer Protection Department: Policy Note*, p. 2.
3. Government of Tamil Nadu (2013-14), *Cooperation, Food and Consumer Protection Department: Policy Note*, www.tn.gov.in, p. 24.
4. Nakkiran, S. and John Winfred, A. (1988), *Cooperative Banking in India*, Rainbow Publications, Coimbatore-30, Tamil Nadu, p.173, 293, 169
5. NABARD (2003-04), *Annual Report*, p.87.
6. RBI (1957), *Report of the Committee on Cooperation in India (Maclagam Committee) 1915*, Bombay.
7. RBI (1992), *Report of the Committee on Licensing of New Urban Cooperative Banks (Marathe Committee)*, Bombay.
8. RBI (2007-08), *Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India*, p. 126
9. www.rbi.org.in.